

Table 1. Performance of 10 BPH-tolerant IR lines in Orissa, India.

Breeding line	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)					Days to 50% flowering	Plant ht (cm)	Silver-shoots (no./hill)	BPH (no./hill)	
	Bhubaneswar			Barachana 1981 R	Mathasahi 1981 R					Mean
	1980 K	1981 R	1982 R							
IR13429-196-1-20	4.8	4.5	2.9	2.6	4.4	3.8	84	77	27	42
IR13429-109-2-2-1	3.8	4.6	3.0	3.0	5.4	4.0	84	73	61	106
IR13420-108-2-2-3	3.6	4.0	3.7	3.2	5.2	3.8	85	71	65	37
IR13429-94-3-2-2-2	—	3.7	—	4.0	4.5	4.1	83	78	—	86
IR15324-117-2-2-3	3.9	2.8	2.9	2.7	2.9	3.0	101	76	43	34
IR17494-32-1-1-3-2	3.8	2.9	2.2	2.5	2.2	2.7	105	78	23	101
IR17525-56-2-2-2	4.5	4.3	3.3	3.1	3.4	3.7	100	85	8	60
IR19657-84-3-2-2	3.3	4.3	2.1	3.0	3.3	3.2	105	80	29	115
IR19661-131-1-2	4.2	2.3	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.6	104	75	56	34
IR19661-364-1-2-3	3.1	4.9	2.2	2.6	2.3	3.0	104	68	58	18
Ratna	2.4	3.6	3.6	3.1	3.0	3.2	83	72	64	326
IR36	4.0	3.4	3.5	3.8	4.5	3.7	87	69	16	130
Jaya	3.3	4.1	3.7	3.3	3.1	3.5	99	85	—	196

^aK = kharif, R = rabi.

their crops often fail. IR36, released in 1980, had moderate to heavy hopper-burn last season.

We tested 10 promising cultures from IRR (Table 1) in 1980-82, using Ratna, IR36, and Jaya as checks. IR-13429-196-1-20 and IR17525-56-2-2-2 were found promising because of favorable grain yield and resistance to BPH and gall midge (GM). Both lines have PTB33 as a parent from which they got their BPH resistance. Table 2 shows similar results from later tests.

IR13429-196-1-20, like Ratna and IR36, matured in 115-120 d. It yielded more than Ratna but slightly less than IR36. It has high tolerance for BPH. IR17525-56-2-2-2 maturity was similar to that of Jaya, but it has a high level of tolerance for GM, BLB, and BPH. In kharif, it yields consistently higher than Jaya (Table 2).

The two breeding lines are being multiplied for distribution to farmers and for their assessment under the minikit program. □

Gall midge (GM) susceptibility of medium- and long-duration rice varieties

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GM *Orseolia oryzae* is an annual problem in Orissa, particularly in wet Season (WS), when it severely damages the rice crop. In 1983 WS we evaluated

Table 2. Performance of two promising BPH-tolerant IR lines in 1981-82 kharif in Orissa, India.

Year, location	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	IR13429-196-1-20	Ratna (check)	IR36 (check)	IR17525-56-2-2-2	Jaya (check)
1981					
Bhubaneswar	3.1	2.6	3.4	4.2	2.1
Jeypore	4.6	4.5	3.9	3.7	5.1
Joshiapur	2.4	2.3	3.7	5.8	3.4
Gombharipalle	2.9	2.5	3.4	4.4	1.9
Keonjhar	3.1	3.6	3.8	—	—
Berhampur	3.6	4.0	4.6	—	2.8
Mean	3.3	3.3	3.8	4.5	3.1
1982					
Bhubaneswar	2.6	2.8	3.2	2.4	3.0
Jeypore	4.4	4.8	3.7	5.8	5.4
Joshiapur	3.4	3.9	4.5	4.7	3.3
Semiliguda	5.4	4.6	4.4	—	1.0
Berhampur	2.0	2.1	2.4	3.3	2.8
Mean	3.6	3.6	3.7	4.0	3.6

medium-duration varieties IET5912 (Sona/Mahsuri), IET7575 (Sona/Manoharsali), IET7284 (Rajeswari/T141), IET7950 (OBS677/IR2071/RPW6-13/W1263), and long-duration varieties IET6315 (Sona/Manoharsali), and IET6903 (RP5-32/Pankaj) for GM resistance at 0, 40, 80, and 120 kg N/ha. Tillers and silvershoots were counted at maximum tillering stage (see table).

Of the six varieties tested, IET7950 produced the most tillers and was most resistant to GM, although it is susceptible to lodging. IET6315 was the most GM-susceptible variety.

Tiller number increased with N dose, but there was no significant difference in the number of silvershoots by N doses. □

GM resistance and effect of N fertilizer on GM infestation of six cultivars, Orissa, India.

Treatment	Tillers/hill	Silvershoots (%)
IET5912	3.6	5.0
IET7575	3.1	4.3
IET7284	3.5	4.7
IET7950	3.7	3.6
IET6315	3.5	5.5
IET6903	3.5	4.5
LSD	0.3*	0.7**
CV (%)	11.8	22.0
N ₀	3.3	4.4
N ₄₀	3.4	4.8
N ₈₀	3.6	4.5
N ₁₂₀	3.7	4.9
LSD	0.20**	ns
CV (%)	9.9	17.1

^aData were converted to square root ($\sqrt{x+0.5}$) then analyzed. * = significant at 5% level, ** = significant at 1% level, ns = not significant.